

Nigeria's Socioeconomic Challenges, Local Government Autonomy As Panacea

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria's Local Governments Councils in Nigeria have, for some time, been emasculated by state governors who literally take charge of their finances, impose lackeys as leaders of local government councils in their states either through sham elections or outrightly illegally appointing caretaker administrators. The adverse effect has been far-reaching. Nigeria today is in some turmoil - socially, economically and in terms of insecurity ravaging the country. This research findings indicate that a key factor responsible for the inflation and insecurity in the country is the failure of local government administration in Nigeria. The study employed the qualitative approach where data was collected and analysed from existing literature and official documents and employs the Structural Functionalism theoretical paradigm in its analysis. The study traces the origin and development of local governments in Nigeria and observes the various attempts by several presidents to strengthen that level of government. It's findings indicate that the local government councils is central to improving on the socioeconomic conditions of Nigeria and Nigerians, it has suffered adverse mismanagement chief of which the lack of autonomy and recommends several legal and political measures to be undertaken to strengthen the local government and make Nigeria developed and to a state of human security towards the Overall development of the Nigerian state.

Keywords: Local Government, Federalism, Autonomy, Federal Accounts Allocation Committee (FAAC), Constitution, Federal Character, Supreme Court

INTRODUCTION

Local Government both as a concept and practical reality across states in the international system has been a matter of intense discussions and disputations among Scholars and Researchers, Politicians and Activists alike. This has elicited multifarious conceptualization of local government across nation-states and political systems. Different concepts and meanings have been adduced globally with reference to local government and its status as a tier of government. (Etebom & Junior, 2022). Nigeria, a federal state has a three-tier federal system that is, the Federal Government, thirty-six (36) State Governments and the third is the 774 local government areas. Perennially, Nigeria has faced multifarious socioeconomic, political and security challenges raging from widespread violence such as the Boko haram insurgency, militancy in the Niger Delta region, separatist movements in the South east geopolitical zones, farmers-herders clashes, internecine conflicts (Ife-Modakeke, Aguleri-Umuleri, Ezza-Ezillo), disputed elections and election-related violence to the multi-dimensional poverty in Nigeria. Analysts have averred that the solution to these challenges lie with the enthronement of 'True Federalism' or for some, fiscal federalism, yet others talk about 'restructuring'. No matter the title with which the agitations are centered around or framed, the general idea is that there is something fundamentally wrong with the current federal arrangement. Whether it is the seeming over-reaching powers of the federal government as encapsulated in the Exclusive List of Legislative Powers in the 1999 Constitution, or the emasculation or gradual killing off of

the local government areas across the country by State Governors, the cacophony of voices are alleging that government is meeting their yearnings and aspirations. At the root of all the agitations, it seems is that the people are not feeling the impact of government in their lives in line with the social contract conception of the state. And the fate of local government councils, which by its nature is meant to be the government closest to the grassroots, is one in which election into offices is a sham, where the revenue yielding functions of local government have been hijacked by their respective state governors and the federal allocations to local governments are almost entirely appropriated by the state governors, leave much to be desired.

THE EVOLUTION AND CONTEMPORARY REALITIES OF LOCAL GOVERNMENT COUNCILS IN NIGERIA

Local Government Councils essentially refers to the level of government closest to the citizens at the grassroots level. It is that tier of the three tiers of government in Nigeria (federal, state and local) that administers and superintends over the daily activities of the citizens whether at the urban, semi-urban or rural levels of society. The country, Nigeria is subdivided into 774 parts each of which is a local government. According to Etebom and Junior (2022), the concept of local government was in effect operational before the advent of colonialism in Nigeria. This is so because even the colonialists, particularly in its indirect rule, leveraged on the pre-existing local governance structure to effectively administer the affairs of the country.

According to Agagu (2011), local government administration in Nigeria has experienced difficulties in its evolution till date, from the Regional differences in the precolonial epoch, through the various constitutional reforms during the colonial era particularly with respect to Sir Frederick Lord Lugard's experimentation through the different post independence republics and military-guided local government creations. Or from pre-colonial, through colonial, independence and republican epoch's military regimes at intervals, the 1976 local government reforms to the third and fourth republics. The product of these today is that there is no uniform system in place for the administration of local governments councils across the federation with respect to upholding democratic principles, relative autonomy as a constitutional tier of government, good governance, due process, rule of law, as well as free, fair and transparent elections for local councils as conducted by their respective states' Independent Electoral Commissions, despite clear, extant constitutional provisions to that effect (Mimiko, 2011, Etebom & Junior, 2022). Aluko, (2010) avers that despite all the movements in the governance and public sector space at the national and sub national levels , there's been some retrogression at the level of local governments with the debilitating implications of true federalism and it's corollary, democracy eluding those at the grassroot. The added implication is a distinct lack of government presence being felt especially with the provision of socio-economic development amd infrastructure at the local level which ought to be a spring board for nationwide security and infrastructural development (Aluko, 2010).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To determine whether the mode of operation of the State-Local Government Joint Account ha retarded Local Government Administration in Nigeria
2. To examine whether the local government administration has been effectively playing statutory socioeconomic and security roles under the practice of our federal system

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the relationship between the management of the Joint State-Local Government account and the poor state of local government administration in Nigeria?
2. How effective have local government administrations been in playing their statutory socioeconomic and security roles under our federal system

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

1. H_R: There is a significant relationship between the management of the State-Local Government Joint Account and the poor state of local government administration in Nigeria;
2. H_R: Local government administration have been effectively playing their statutory socioeconomic and security roles under the practice of our federal system

METHODOLOGY

This Research will adopt the use of the Survey method of data collection. It will also adopt the use of secondary data for the analysis. This data collected will be reviewed and analyzed to draw conclusions based on the research questions and hypothesis that form the foundations for this research effort. Secondary data collection and analysis involves the review and use of existing data. This achieves a number of goals

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

According to Paleker (2006), there are three broad categories of theories of federalism. These are the classical, origin and functional theories of federalism. He posits that the major proponents of the classical theory of federalism include K C Wheare, A V Dicey, R Garran, Bryce, Moore and Jethrow Brown. Paleker (2006) quoting Garan defined federalism as a type of governmental system whereby sovereignty and the powers of the state is distributed between the federal/central government and the local governments, such that either of them, within their respective spheres is independent of the other. Lord Bryce on his part described the two levels of government as distinct and separate in the performance of their action while comparing the federal system to a factory where a dual set of equipments working with an interplay of their wheels, while each set of machinery carries out its work without impacting adversely on the other. (Paleker, 2006). The renowned Federalism authority, K C Wheare, as quoted by Paleker, (2006) puts the logic advanced by Lord Bryce to task when he avers that 'does a system of government embody predominantly a division of power between general and regional authorities, each of which, in its own sphere, is coordinate with the other and independent of them? If so, the government is federal'. This suggests a two tier government, general and regional, and that is the central theme of the classical school of federalism. The relevance of the classical school of federalism is the fact that it identifies the precondition of distinct and independent levels of government along central and sub-national levels, as a precondition for effective federalism. This provides a form of template for the evaluation of the propriety and functionality of a federal state like Nigeria where for example, a tier of government, ie the local government areas have almost become moribund and ineffective due to the overbearing influence of another level of government. A situation where this occurs, its pertinent to ask if this will not lead to a failure of the system and government's ability to provide the public goods.

LOCAL ADMINISTRATION IN THE PRE-COLONIAL AND COLONIAL ERA

Before the onset of colonialism, Nigeria has been experiencing some form of highly developed local administration from the Old Oyo Empire in the so-called, Western Region, to the Hausa Fulani Empire/ Empire in the Northern Region and to the acephalous kingdoms of the then Eastern Region. Across board, there were established traditional instrumental governance and administrative apparatus in effect which served as the platform upon which the colonialist launched their native administration. These traditional administrative arrangements had at the helm kings, Emirs, Obas and heads of families, depending on what region one was at, exercising local administrative control over their subjects using the traditional councils in existing communities in pre colonial Nigeria. (Ola & Tonwe, 2009). The nature of these precolonial, local councils include a centralised system of government in the Hausa-Fulani Emirate, a decentralised system of government in the Old Oyo Empire and a no clear-cut government system in the acephalous Igbo /Eastern Region. Rather, the latter operated a system that was family compound controlled with every such family compound coming together to constitute the local administrative structure in each community (Etebom, 2022).

The 1914 Amalgamation of the Colony and Protectorates of Northern and Southern Nigeria also led to the introduction of the system of Indirect Rule or Native Administration across Nigeria. This system of Indirect Rule was largely effective and successful in the Hausa-Fulani Emirate in the Northern Region of Nigeria and the Old Oyo Empire, where incidentally, the traditional institutions were very well organized and respected by all. The purposeful adoption of the system of Indirect Rule by the Colonialists was to preserve and leverage the authority of local institutions for convenience and effective administration. The native administration system had evolved over a several decades and the pace of development had intensified as a result of initiatives from varied sources and directions such as the establishment of regional councils and a wide ranging review of the system of native authority by the Sir Arthur Richards Constitution of 1946 (Onajite, 1946). Furthermore, the colonial objective could not be actualised if they upended and replaced the well established system of norms, traditions and native institutions of the colonised people. (Mukoro, 2003).. The McPherson Constitution of 1957 also introduced what it termed the 'local council law' in Nigeria following from the native authority law enacted by the Sir Arthur Richards constitutional reforms of 1954 while the key actors were chief and council, the chief-in-council, the federated native authority county and municipal councils. (Etebom and Junior, 2022).

The Eastern Regional Administration pioneered a paradigm shift in the mechanism for the administration of local government as early as 1950. This was due to the widespread disillusionment with the system of native authority due largely to corruption and the already highlighted acephalous nature and custom of the people. (Agagu, 2008, Etebom and Junior, 2022). There was also a comprehensive overhaul of the local government statutes which were instituted in the 1957 constitution while the Northern Region largely refrained from reviewing the native authority system bequeathed to it by the Colonialists' Indirect Rule since it aligned with its cultural and traditional system of governance that predated the advent of colonialism (Etebom and Junior, 2022).

LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN THE POST COLONIAL ERA

As earlier noted, local government administration under Sir Frederick Lord Lugard's colonial rule was structured under the system of Indirect Rule or Native Administration. And this system experienced varying levels of success across Regions. While it succeeded exceptionally in the

Northern Region, largely due to the pre-existing and well established, centralised traditional system of local administration, the situation was radically different in the then Eastern Region as the Indirect Rule administrative mechanism was at variance with the acephalous cultural and traditional system prevalent there. The period after independence, particularly between 1960 and 1976, was central to the development of the local government in Nigeria. During the period of colonialism, the operation and mechanism of local government administration varied depending on the region in question as local government areas in each region developed at their own pace but what is common to them all, as Etebom and Junior (2022) put it, the history of local governments, post independence is sine qua non to military rule as virtually all developments recorded post independence in local government administration were embarked upon by the military. Furthermore, the reforms that were put in place, the 1966 coup, the hijack literally by the Regional and then State governments, which was succeeded by the rolliut of different systems of local government across the country further diminished the chances of local governments. (Mukoro, 2003; Ola & Tonwe, 2009). In the North for example local government reforms led to the watering down of the powers of the Emir and the scrapping of the divisional administration and the system of native authority. In the South East region, a system was introduced which was aptly tagged "Development Administration" with local administration replaced by local government. Further, in the South West, the Sole Administrators system was introduced and then replaced with the Local Advisory Council which was a 10 member Advisory committee while the District Officers served as chairman. The critical element in these reforms was the transfer of powers, finances and staff from the local government to state ministries. With the increasing number of states from 12 in 1967 to 19 in 1976, there was a marked shortfall in revenue accruing to state governments. To change this, state governments began usurping the powers and functions of local governments that were deemed lucrative / revenue yielding. This resulted in the pauperisation of local governments councils as they were now cash-strapped and increased overbearing influence of state governments. The Local Government Councils were thus unable to embark on their constitutional roles (Egonmwan, 1990; Etebom and Junior, 2022). In a bid to reverse the ugly trend, the federal military administration introduced the Public Service Review Commission. Part of the terms of reference of the commission was the review of the Nigerian Local Government System. Although it's recommendations included ways to enhance the state of local government but the white paper wasn't released before a counter coup outside the military regime. It however led to the 1976 Reform Guidelines for Local Governments and the enactment of Local Government Edicts by State Governors.

THE 1976 REFORMS OF LOCAL GOVERNMENTS

A paradigm shift was recorded in 1976 in local government administration in the country. with the introduction of the 1976 Local Government Reforms. That Reform policy was aptly described by several scholars as a watershed in the evolution of local governments in Nigeria. Etebom & Junior (2022), quoting Ola (1979) stated that it was the first time the federal government was acting directly in a way that unified local government system across the states in the country. It was also the first time the local government was being recognised as a tier of government. This recognition as a tier of government, with defined boundaries, implicit functions and clearly defined provisions of human and material resources to work with, was the distinguishing factors from earlier reforms. The federal government noted then that the local government has had their powers incrementally whittled down by state governors who encroached on the exclusive preserve of local governments in terms of funding and institutions

making them moribund, modest progress impossible due to politicking making the people seemingly alienated from government even at the most basic level (Etebom and Junior, 2022). Agagu (2011) adds that the overall objective of the Local Government Reforms was to revive and revitalise the local government system nationwide with regards to the functions, structure, financial resources, relationship with state governments and traditional institutions as well as law enforcement. (Etebom & Junior, 2022).

The reforms clearly listed the local government as a third tier of the Nigerian federation. Section 5 of the reforms provided for the exclusive, concurrent and permissive (residual) lists of legislative powers. These powers and functions were subsequently enshrined in the 4th Schedule of both the 1979 and 1999 constitutions of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended). Some of the highlights of the 1976 Local Government Reforms included:

A. The introduction of a multipurpose, single tier local government structure for the entire country with the population of each ranging between 150,000 and 800,000 indigenes; B. Funding was required to be from the federation account via the Federal Accounts Allocation Commission (FAAC) and internally generated revenue (IGR);

C. The relationship between the host state and their respective local government councils was one of superordinate and subordinate status with each state establishing a Ministry of Local Government (and Chieftaincy Affairs);

D. The express exclusion of the traditional institutions from direct involvement in the running of local government councils. The traditional Rulers were only assigned consultative and advisory roles while the local government councils played a direct supervisory role;

E. The 1976 local government reforms also allowed for democratic processes with popular participation in the election of representatives in all the local government councils in the country ie election of chairmen and councillors representing local government areas and wards respectively, were to be by freely contested direct elections. For all the positives highlighted however, there were some notable drawbacks in the 1976 local government reforms. These include

A. Local government administrations were not empowered to maintain law and order. This denied local governments the powers of enforcement of bye-laws and other governmental legislations

B. The universal rule it emplaced which made local government administration uniform across the country meant that the local governments lost their individual identities based on the uniqueness and diversity of their localities (Adeyeye, 2016; Etebom & Junior, 2022).

It's noteworthy that the 1976 Local Government Reforms failed because its policy recommendations could not be fully implemented, particularly the democratisation of local governments institutions. However, while the reforms did not succeed on its own merit, it served as the foundation for the enactment of constitutional provisions on local government in the 1979 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, which in turn served as the Grund Norm and elixir for all subsequent constitutional provisions in the 1989 Constitution, 1999 Constitution and all subsequent amendments of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. During the second republic, local government elections were held in December 1976 throughout the country on a zero-party basis. Between then and 1979 when the Shagari administration came on board, the Military regime in power took noteworthy and laudable steps to address all challenges encountered in the process of implementation of the 1976 local government reforms with particular reference to funding and human resources. It's interesting to note that throughout the second republic, 1979 to 1983, local government neither had the benefit of experiencing democratic norms as elections were never held over the period as state

governors dissolved the local government administrations across the federation immediately the civilian administration of Shehu Shagari came into office. This was the situation until the military returned on the 31st of December, 1983. During the period under review, rather than hold elections to produce democratically elected leaders for the local government councils, the political class appointed management committees to run the affairs of local government councils. This was rather ironic as the constitutional guaranteed and legal means of choosing leaders for local governments was jettisoned during the supposed civilian political rule. The succeeding administration led by Buhari, upon coming into office in 1983, immediately dissolved the so-called management committees of local government councils across the federation and set in motion initiatives to revive and revitalise the local government administration which was the constitutional third tier of government in the country. It set the 1976 local government reforms policy as its template, appointed senior civil servants as sole administrators of local government areas and inaugurated a 20-man committee led by Ibrahim Dasuki to review the challenges besetting the local government system in Nigeria. The committee in its report, upheld the 1976 local government reforms and noted that the challenges were rather operational in nature. It highlighted the lack of equitable provision of Social amenities across the wards in each local government as well as the deleterious roles of state governments during the last administration. On a sour note however, the Gen Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida led counter coup d'etat in August, 1985 meant that no white paper was either released nor was the report of the Dasuki committee implemented by the Buhari regime.

THE STATE OF LOCAL GOVERNMENTS UNDER THE BABANGIDA ADMINISTRATION (1985-1993)

The General Ibrahim Babangida Administration gave another breath of life to local government councils in Nigeria. This it achieved by giving local government administrations all the apparatus and accoutrement of a presidential system of Government to ebb the gradual reversal of local government autonomy. First it directed the abrogation of the Ministry of Local Government (and Chieftaincy Affairs) in all states of the federation - a tool the state governors were using to micromanage the local government areas in their respective states. (Ola, 2009). Secondly unlike the Shagari administration, the Babangida led Administration, conducted local government council elections in all states of the federation on the 12th of December, 1987 on a zero-party basis. Thirdly, the Babangida led Administration scrapped the State - Local Government Joint Account and rather sent the revenue accruing to the respective local governments from the federation account to them directly. It further set up a Civil Service Reforms Committee in 1988 led Prof. Philip Adedotun. Among its terms of reference was to propose an wholesale reform to the Administrative Structure and funding of local government areas across the federation. It also included the professionalisation of the local government work force to enhance productivity and service delivery at that level of government bureaucracy. The white paper of government on this 1988 Reforms indicated that the local government chairman shall be the chief Executive and Chief Accounting Officer of their respective local government councils, (although as the Chief Accounting Officer, he is not allowed to sign official cheques), made provisions for the appointment of Supervisory Councillors by the Chairman who shall form part of the executive council and head various departments within the local government council. The 1988 Local Government Reforms also provided for popularly elected Councillors who shall each come from the different wards in the local government area. The elected Councillors shall make up the

legislative arm of the local government. A subsequent election was held in December, 1990 on a partisan basis where again, the elections led to the direct election of Chairmen, Vice Chairman and Councillors of local government councils. (Etebom and Junior, 2022).

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Major highlights of the 1988 local government reforms Guidelines or the basic constitutional provisions amendment decree of 1991 include:

A. The Elected Ward Representatives (Councillors) shall constitute the legislative arm of the local government area charged with lawmaking powers, while one of the Councillors shall be elected from amongst themselves, as the leader of the legislative arm of the local government;

B. The Chairman shall be the Chief Executive officer and a member of the local government council;

C. Supervisors (or Supervisory Councillors) shall be appointed by the Chairman from within or without the local government council. They shall be in charge of a portfolio or responsible for a department within the council. They shall make up the executive arm of the council along with the chairman and vice chairman of the local government;

D. A secretary to the local government shall be appointed who will serve as the Chief Administrative Officer of the local government council.

From the foregoing, it's observed that the Executive and Legislative arms of government are properly accounted for in the local government councils. However the Judiciary is not provided for as is the case with other tiers of government that is, the state and federal government. The 1989 constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria further entrenched provisions that addressed the local government Administration on the country. First, it increased the number of local government areas from 307 to 449, states were empowered to create a maximum of seven development areas which correspond historically with the historical and traditional tiers, demographic considerations and administrative experience. A third provision of the 1989 constitution which relates to local government administration was the requirement that the State Auditor General audits the accounts of all local government areas annually and the audited report be presented to the State's House of Assembly. One thing is clear from the foregoing, as Agagu (2011) avers, the Babangida Administration introduced the highest number of local government reforms in the history of Nigeria with the overall objective being to make the local government councils the third tier of government in practice.

A noteworthy last line is that the several reforms introduced by successive military administrations led to the present structure of local governments in Nigeria.

NIGERIA'S LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN THE FOURTH REPUBLIC

During the brief transition government led by Gen Abdus-Salami Anubakar, after the demise of Gen Sani Abacha, local government council elections were held across the country in December, 1998 as a first step in a series of elections that included the state legislative and presidential elections. Their tenure was for three years. Significantly, this local government councils elections were conducted by the national military government. Upon the completion of their three year tenure, in 2002, the general expectation from the populace was that elections would be held especially because the military junta had now handed over to a civilian president and elected state governors and national and state assembly members. The challenge included

the fact that the elected leaders were not interested in promoting democratic values at the grassroots and the 1999 constitution did not place much emphasis on the process of election of leaders at the local government level unlike the 1989 constitution which gave much attention to issues relating to local government from process and guidelines for elections to powers of elected local government officials to their tenure in office as well as local government service (Etebom and Junior, 2022; Agagu, 2011; Ola, 2009).

All these were however sadly not enacted as part of provisions of the 1999 constitution (as amended). This is the foundation of the present challenges that the local government councils in Nigeria are grappling with. Etebom and Junior (2022) quoting Ola, 2005 notes that this is a period of uncertainty on the fate and future of local government areas in Nigeria because although the 1999 constitution makes provision for the establishment, structure, funding, structure and composition of local government areas, there's still high level of uncertainty surrounding local governments and their officials. Rather they have been at the mercy of state governors who whimsically dissolve, suspend and upend elected local government council officials and often impose caretaker committees or hold sham elections which put lackeys at the helm of local government councils. (Agagu, 2011; Etebom and Junior, 2022).

THE FATE OF LOCAL COUNCILS IN NIGERIA TODAY

Etebom and Junior, (2022) unequivocally assert that the fate of local government councils as the third tier of government in Nigeria today is at variance with the extent provisions on local governments in the 1999 constitution (as amended) as well as the 1976 Local Government Reforms which among others made provisions for a universally consistent structure for local government councils across the country with democratically elected officials. The challenge however which is being exploited by state governments is the ambiguity surrounding the place of states houses of assembly and their respective governors. The reality is that most of the statutory functions of the local government councils have been literally hijacked by state governments. According to Etebom and Junior, 2022; Adeyeye, 2016; Aghayere, 2010 and Ola & Tonwe, 2009; the functions of the local governments have been delineated into three broad categories viz the general, concurrent and exclusive functions.

1. The general functions of the local government include the discharge of duties imposed on it by law, assisting in maintaining law and order as well as good governance within its defined boundaries, prevent lawbreakers from committing offences and reporting any act or conduct that is capable of breaching public peace to the appropriate legal cum judicial authority.
2. The second category of duties enshrined in the constitution to be carried out by the local government administration are the exclusive functions ie functions that they can exclusively legislate upon by way of bye-laws. These include: the establishment, control and management of vehicle parks and markets; sanitation, refuse and sewage disposal as well as sanitary inspections; establishment, control and regulation of abattoirs; registration of births, deaths and weddings; establishment, management and control of cemeteries and mortuaries; provision and maintenance of public conveniences; provision and maintenance of recreational and community centres; establishment and management of parks, gardens and open spaces. The list of exclusive functions further include the licencing of vehicles like bicycles and trucks; licencing, regulation and supervision of eateries and bakeries; control and regulation of advertisement services and use of loud speakers in and around public buildings and spaces; naming or numbering of roads and streets, as well as buildings and plots of lands; collection of vehicular parking fees; regulation and collection of property taxes and sundry designated

revenues sources and rates including radio and television licences; as well as regulation of traffic and parking.

3. The third category of local government functions as earlier noted is the concurrent list of duties. The concurrent functions refer to those roles that the state governments as well as other agencies and organisations are empowered to carry out or partake in the performance of these functions especially where the local government councils as constituted do not have the capacity to perform such functions. These include provision of primary health care facilities like maternity and communicable diseases clinics, ambulances services, primary educational institutions / schools, development of agricultural and natural resources like forestry, public enlightenment and information dissemination, water supply, grading and tarring of trunk C roads, street lights and drainages, promoting local arts and culture, water supply, pollution control prevention of street begging, prostitution and destitutes. The concurrent list of functions also include establishment of orphanage homes and homes for the destitute, provision of public utilities like water boards for water supply, development of mass / public housing programmes, town planning, control of soil erosion among others.

CHALLENGES FACED BY LOCAL GOVERNMENT COUNCILS UNDER THE CURRENT DISPENSATION

The local government councils in Nigeria are in this fourth republic indeed face a number of challenges. These range from lack of democracy. By this it is meant that state governments do not usually conduct elections for local governments in majority of the states. And in the few where elections are held, it is marred by either rigging of elections or imposition of candidates to appointment of sole administrators. This is at variance with the clear provisions of the 1999 constitution which stipulates that the system of local government run by democratically elected local government councils is guaranteed under the constitution. Furthermore, the other major challenge besetting our local government councils in Nigeria today is the lack of autonomy despite being a constitutional tier of government. Although the 1999 constitution makes provision for the independence of local government councils, the situation local governments face across the states is more or less the whimsical dispositions of their respective state governors. This is perhaps the greatest impediment impacting adversely on the deepening of democratic values at the grassroots particularly with regards to citizens' participation, popular representation, efficient and effective service delivery, and good governance. (Etebom, 2022). We cannot envisage local government autonomy where the citizens are not allowed to elect their leaders themselves or funds accruing to local governments are illegally taken over by state governments.

CONCLUSION

This paper dealt with the challenges besetting the third tier of government in Nigeria and its inability to deliver on its constitutional roles. The panacea therefore is in granting the local government full and unencumbered autonomy in public policy making and financial autonomy. In addressing these issues, this paper highlighted the historical, underlying issues besetting the local government administration in the country as the level of government closest to the populace. These challenges, the paper notes have hampered the ability of local governments in discharging their constitutional roles as captured in the residual lists of legislative powers enshrined in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended). This paper therefore calls for the full and immediate implementation of the recent Supreme Court ruling on full autonomy for local governments in Nigeria as it is not just now a constitutional matter but now also a final adjudication of the Judicial branch of government. This paper concludes

that this will lead to the amelioration of the immense socio-economic challenges the country is facing. And recommends that there should be prosecution of state actors who act ultra vires so that local governments in Nigeria can experience a new lease of life so they can play their statutory roles and meeting their obligations towards enhancing sustainable, socio-economic development across the country.

REFERENCES

- Adamolekun, L. (ed.) (2005), *Public Administration in Africa: Main Issues and Selected Country Studies*, Ibadan, Spectrum Books Ltd.
- Adeyemo, D. O. (2005), "Local Government Autonomy in Nigeria: A Historical Perspectives" *Journal of Social Sciences*, Vol.x No.II
- Adeyemo, D.O. 1996. "Federalism and the Logic of Local Government Autonomy in Nigeria". *Nigerian Journal of Local Government Studies*, 16. December 1996 O.A.U. Ile-Ife.
- Agagu, A.A. (2011). *Theory and Practice of Local Government*, Policy and Consultants Ltd, Akure
- Agagu, A. (2004). *Continuity and Change in Local Government Administration and the Politics of Underdevelopment*. In: Agagu, A. & Ola, R. (eds). *Development Agenda of Nigeria State*. Ibadan: Fiag Publishers.
- Agbakoba, O. and Ogbonna, H. (2004). *Local Government Administration and Development in Nigeria*, Lagos: HURILAWS. Ajayi, K. (2000). *Justification and Theories of Local Government*. In: Ajayi, K. (ed). *Theory and Practice of Local Government Ado-Ekiti*. Department of Political Science, University of Ado-Ekiti.
- Aghayere, V.O (2010). *Local Government in Nigeria since 1950* in Ola, R.F and Imhanlahimi, J.E (ed). *Nigeria Political System: Trends Perspectives*, University of Benin Press, Benin City
- Aluko, J.O. (2010). *Local Government Elections and The Challenges of Democratic Governance in Nigeria*, [www.nigeriaworld.com>articles>aug](http://www.nigeriaworld.com/articles/aug) accessed on /07/2017.
- Awotokun, A.M. and D.O. Adeyemo 1999. "Local Government in Nigeria". A critical Exploration". *Journal of Public Affairs Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria*.
- Etebom J M and Junior H W, (2022) 'The Historical Development Of Local Government Administration and Its Contemporary Realities In Nigeria' *The Journalish: Social and Government*. Vol. 3 No. 1
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (1976). *The 1976 Guidelines on Local Government Reforms in Nigeria*, Federal Ministry of Information, Lagos.

Federal Republic of Nigeria. (1999). The 1999 Constitution (as amended). Lagos, Federal Government Press

Gboyega, A. (1983). Local Government Reforms in Nigeria in Philips Mawhood (ed) Local Government in Third World, Chichester John Wiley and Sons.

Egonmwan, J.A (1990). Principles and Practices of Local Government in Nigeria, S.M.O. Aka & Brother Press, Benin City.

Nwabueze B.O. 1983. The Presidential Constitution of Nigeria. London: Sweet and Maxwell. Nigerian. Journal of Public Administration and Local Government. Vol. 2 No. 2 1984.

Ola, R. F. (1984). Local Administration in Nigeria. London: Kegan Paul International.

Ola, R. F. & Tonwe, D. A. (2003). Local Government Administration and Local Government in Nigeria, Trust Publishing, Lagos.

Ola, R. F. and Tonwe, D.A. (2009). Local Government Administration and Local Government in Nigeria, Lagos: Amfitop Book.

Onajide, M.O (1997). Evolution of Local Government and National Economy in Nigeria, Comfort Press and Publishing Company Ltd, Ikeja Lagos.

Stepan, A. (2005) 'Federalism and Democracy: Beyond the US Model', in Karmis, D. and Norman, W. (eds.), Theories of Federalism: A Reader, New York and Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.

Suberu, R. (2001) Federalism and Ethnic Conflict in Nigeria, Washington, D.C.: United States Institute of Peace Press.

Wheare, K. C. (1963) Federal Government, 4th ed., London: Oxford University Press.